

**Spectrophotometric Determination of
Ruthenium(III) and Rhodium(III) with
n-Amylthioglycolate**

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*Manuscript received 7 June 1991, revised 16 September 1991,
accepted 28 October 1991*

A survey of literature revealed that ruthenium(III) and rhodium(III) react with most of the organic reagents only at high temperature¹ requiring 3–24 h depending on the nature of the reactant. Ruthenium(III) and rhodium(III) have also been determined spectrophotometrically after the extraction of their complexes into molten naphthalene (after stirring² for 30–40 min). However, this method is inconvenient and time-consuming as the metal complex has to be separated by filtration and the volume of the organic solvent has to be readjusted. Here we present a simple, sensitive and selective method for the determination of ruthenium(III) and rhodium(III) after extraction of their complexes into chloroform. As ruthenium(III) reacts with n-amylthioglycolate (ATG) at room temperature and rhodium(III) after heating (60–70°) for 2–5 min, conditions have been developed for their simultaneous determinations in synthetic mixtures.

Experimental

A digital pH meter and a Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer were used. All solvents and reagents were of analytical reagent grade. Ruthenium(III) and rhodium(III) solutions were prepared by dissolving their chlorides in acidulated distilled water and standardised³. n-Amylthioglycolate (ATG) was prepared by the reported method⁴. A 0.1% solution of the reagent was prepared in ethanol and standardised titrimetrically using mercury(II) acetate as titrant and diphenylcarbazone as internal indicator.

Procedure: To a known volume of each of the metal ion solution was added the reagent solution (1.5 ml). The pH was then adjusted to 5.8 (ruthenium) and 9.5 (rhodium) and the appropriate buffer (2.0 ml) and potassium chloride solution (1M; 1.0 ml) were added to give a 0.1 M concentration after dilution to 10 ml. Rhodium(III) solution was heated on a water-bath (60–70°) for 5 min. These solutions were shaken with chloroform (10 ml) for 5 min. The chloroform layer was then poured onto anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g). A portion of each of these solutions was taken and absorbance was measured at 365 nm for ruthenium and at 345 nm for rhodium against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The ruthenium complex shows an absorption maximum at 365 nm, whereas the rhodium complex at 345 nm; the absorption of the reagent being negligible in this range. The effect of pH was studied using dilute perchloric acid and ammonia solutions. The absorbance values were constant in the pH range 4.8–9.3 for ruthenium and 8.5–12.5 for rhodium. The complexes were extracted completely at these pH ranges. It was observed that with the addition of 0.5 ml and 0.4 ml of 0.1% reagent to ruthenium (50 µg) and rhodium (21 µg), extractions were quantitative. The extractions were found to be quantitative if the electrolyte concentration was more than 0.05 M. Therefore, 0.1 M potassium chloride was used in 10 ml of the final solution throughout the study. Other electrolytes such as sodium chloride, sodium acetate and potassium nitrate (0.01–1.0 M) can also be used. It was observed that ruthenium(III) forms a complex with ATG at room temperature, whereas rhodium(III) on heating (60–70°) for 3–5 min. After complexation the extraction of these complexes into chloroform was very rapid and no change was observed in the absorbance when the shaking time was varied from 1 to 10 min. The ruthenium and rhodium complexes were extractable (percentages of extraction shown in parenthesis) in chloroform (99.8, 99.9%), carbon tetrachloride (90, 91%), ethyl acetate (85, 87%), 1,2-dichloromethane (88, 90%), diethyl ether (77, 80%), isobutyl methyl ketene (94, 96%) and butyl acetate (93, 95%, respectively). Chloroform was found to be the best solvent. The effect of the volume ratio on the absorbance was examined.

The absorbance remained constant upto 40 ml of the aqueous phase. However, with further increase in volume of the aqueous phase the absorbance decreased. Hence in all further experiments, the volume of the aqueous phase was maintained at 10 ml for convenience. The composition of the complexes, viz. $\text{Ru}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{S})_3$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{S})_3$, was established by using Job's method of continuous variation and mole-ratio method.

Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 5–98 µg of ruthenium and 2–45 µg of rhodium in 10 ml of final solution. The molar absorptivity values calculated for ruthenium and rhodium are $5.2 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3$ and $1.63 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with relative standard deviations of 0.8 and 0.9%, respectively. The Sandell's sensitivities for ruthenium and rhodium are calculated to be 0.02 and 0.006 µg cm^{-2} , respectively.

In general for interference studies, various anions and cations were added individually to a solution containing 50 µg of ruthenium or 21 µg of rhodium and the tolerance limits are as follows for both of them; fluoride, chloride, bromide, iodide, acetate, nitrate, sulphate, thiosulphate, metabisulphite, carbonate, phosphate and thiourea (10 mg each); citrate, oxalate, tartrate, nitrite and EDTA (5 mg each); Pb^{II} , Bi^{III} , Cd^{II} , Mo^{VI} , U^{VI} , Zn^{II} and Cr^{III} (1.3 mg each); V^{V} , Pt^{IV} , Ir^{III} , Au^{III} , Os^{VIII} and Rh^{III} (0.6 mg each). Co^{II} (0.6 mg) and Ni^{II} (0.9 mg) are tolerable in the presence of 0.5 ml 1% EDTA solution, Fe^{II} (0.06 mg) with 2 ml of 5% sodium fluoride solution and Pd^{II} (0.4 mg) with 2 ml of 5% solution of sodium thiosulphate. Cu^{II} (1.5 mg) is tolerable in the case of ruthenium but interfered in the determination of rhodium, and it can be masked with 0.5 ml of 1% EDTA solution. The interference of ruthenium in the determination of rhodium was eliminated by pre-extracting ruthenium into chloroform, while rhodium which is left in the aqueous phase can be determined after heating (60–70°) the contents for 2–5 min.

For testing the validity of the method it was applied to synthetic mixtures of the following percentage composition: (i) Ru^{III} , 15; Ir^{III} , 10; Au^{III} , 10; Pd^{IV} , 5; Os^{VIII} , 40; Fe^{III} , 20; (ii) Ru^{III} , 20; Pt^{IV} , 30; Co^{II} , 10; Ni^{II} , 10; Mo^{VI} , 20; Ir^{III} , 10 (for ruthenium), (iii) Rh^{III} , 5; Au^{III} , 50; Pd^{II} , 15; Ir^{III} , 20; Pt^{IV} , 10; (iv) Rh^{III} , 10; Au^{III} , 50; Pd^{II} , 20; Fe^{II} , 10; Os^{VIII} , 10 (for rhodium). Each of the mixture was treated with 5% hydrazine solution (1 ml) and heated gently to dryness. The residue was mixed with a mixture of KOH and KNO_3 (8 : 1; 3 g) and heated at 800° for 30 min. The cooled melt was leached with water, acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml) and diluted to 100 ml. To an aliquot of the synthetic sample was added ATG solution (1.5 ml) and pH was adjusted to 5.5 with acetate buffer solution; to it were added 1% EDTA (0.5 ml) and 5% sodium thiosulphate (2 ml) solutions and ruthenium was determined by extraction at room temperature in the presence of potassium chloride (1.0 ml). The aqueous

phase was treated with ATG solution (1.5 ml) and pH was adjusted to 9.5 with ammonia buffer (pH 9.5; 2.0 ml) and rhodium was determined by the general procedure. In the determination of rhodium, the interference due to most of the cations can be avoided by pre-extraction at room temperature.

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